

Mapping the Real and Fictional Geographies of Avignon's Theatre Festivals

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As part of the ERC project STAGE, which aims to develop a framework for *performing arts analytics* (Bardiot 2021), this study applies quantitative analysis and data-driven AI methods to revisit the history of theatre institutions. In theatre and performing arts studies, the use of digital tools and computational approaches remains in its infancy and is rarely extended beyond the analysis of dramatic texts (Fischer 2019; Champion 2016). This study employs mapping techniques, Natural Language Processing (NLP) and Large Language Models (LLM) to examine the international aspirations and programming choices of two theatre festivals held annually in the French town of Avignon.

Every July, Avignon hosts two parallel performing art events: the official Avignon theatre festival known as the IN, established in 1947 by Jean Vilar as a laboratory for public cultural policies (Loyer and Baecque 2016), and the OFF festival that gained visibility after 1968 as an alternative festival with a horizontal structure, where partner venues independently curate their own program (Rumello 2016). This paper consists of two parts. First, it outlines the ongoing workflow used to build an explorable dataset from the programmes and playbills of both the IN and the OFF festivals. The IN is regarded as one of the most prestigious theatre events on a global scale, with over 2,000 performances presented since 1947. The OFF, on the other hand, is described as the world's "largest" theatre market (Germain 2013), featuring over 1,000 performances annually. Combining the archives of the festivals offers an unprecedented resource for performing arts analytics. Second, we use the above data in a case study comparing the international aspirations and geographies of the two festivals.

In 2013, stage director Olivier Py was appointed head of the IN festival. He inaugurated his first festival edition with an ambitious statement about the festival's international identity. For Py, Avignon was — and would remain — a meeting point for artists from "five continents" who would explore both "social and imaginary" frontiers, taking audiences on a journey "from elsewhere to here and from here to elsewhere" (Py 2014). Drawing on this statement, our goal is to measure the international dimension of the festival and assess the extent to which such imaginary trips to "elsewhere" actually took place for the audience. To do so, we examine both the 'real' geography of the two festivals, i.e. the countries of origin of participating artists, and the 'imagined' one, i.e., the narrative places and locations evoked within the fictional universes of each show.

We compare the first years of Olivier Py's tenure (2014–2017) with the last years of the preceding period (2010–2013), when the IN festival was directed by Hortense Archambault and Vincent Baudriller, examining how trends develop across both festivals. Our corpus includes festival programs and playbills encompassing the entire history of both, a valuable yet understudied resource. We process the OFF's festival programmes, in born-digital PDF format, using the open-source library pyMuPdf (Artifex Software 2024) to extract the information

about each show, including its country of origin and its synopsis. Using various web scraping tools, we retrieve similar information for shows programmed at the IN from the festival's online archives. We consider theatre programmes as the most reliable historical source compared to other databases or official reports that are often incomplete.

The second part of the paper showcases the research potential of the above data through a case study on the international identity of the two festivals. As exemplified in Olivier Py's statement, the IN festival seeks an international perspective, bringing together artists from five continents and addressing themes that extend beyond a European context. Meanwhile, with over 1,000 shows per year, the OFF has become a prime destination for both French and international productions. The coexistence of the two festivals may also lead to bidirectional influences, where programming strategies in one festival impact the other and vice versa. To explore how the international aspirations of the two festivals intersect, we create maps to trace the evolution of the festivals' geographies over time. We calculate the ratio of national to international shows programmed in the first years under Olivier Py and compare it with the corresponding ratio from the previous period under Hortense Archambault and Vincent Baudriller. We then examine the OFF during the same periods. We compare these maps to: (a) assess the impact of Olivier Py's leadership on the international identity of the IN, (b) examine whether the programming choices of the OFF exhibited similar trends.

We find that the international dimension of the IN festival under Olivier Py presents a limited yet notable change. While the increase in the percentage of international productions programmed is marginal, they are less European-centred and spread in more production cities globally, including several productions from South America, the Middle East and the Balkans. We observe however that the programming choices of the OFF festival do not exhibit similar trends during the study periods. We also observe that the distribution of the IN festival's international productions per continent is skewed. This is due to thematic focus of specific years, such as 2013 (Ivory Coast) and 2017 (Africa). We interpret these findings as evidence for the different conceptions the two festivals have regarding their international dimension. For certain years, the IN's curation looks at specific geographies in reaction to political or artistic discourse, bringing selected international shows to Avignon from areas which are not represented in later years. In contrast, even though the OFF festival features a low percentage of international productions, the festival consistently includes productions from non-European areas, indicating a slow but steady trend toward internationalization. Lastly, the OFF festival consistently features productions from overseas French territories, which are absent from the IN.

In our next exercise, we examine how the 'imagined' geography of the two festivals evolves during the same period. In literary studies, recent computational approaches combine Natural Language Processing (NLP) models, such as BERT (Devlin et al. 2019), with annotation tools to identify words with spatial references within a text. State-of-the-art NER techniques use pre-trained models on large, annotated datasets and typically perform well in identifying geographical references (Jurafsky and Martin 2024). For example, the popular BookNLP toolkit achieves an accuracy of 90% (Bamman 2024). More recent methods further fine-tune existing NER systems to recognize non-named spatial elements, such as "mountain",

“forest”, “cave”, or “city” (Kalabgi et al. 2024). LLMs have also been tested in similar tasks and are also found to perform well (Tangherlini and Chen 2024). However, to our knowledge, these tools have not yet been tested on a corpus of theatre synopses.

We test the French version of Stanza (Qi and al. 2020) and Anthropic’s Claude “sonnet-4-20250514” model to extract named entities referring to narrative locations from the synopses of shows and find that Anthropic’s model performs better for the needs of this study, as it can filter narrative locations from other irrelevant spatial entities mentioned in the synopses. We use this information to compute the median distance between the production and narrative locations for each show programmed in the IN and OFF festivals during the study period. We also create maps (with Kepler, kepler.gl) to visualize these connections for the two festivals, grouping productions by continent. We compare these maps to examine how the audience’s “social and imaginary” geographical horizons are shaped across the two festivals. We find that while most European productions refer to Europe, many of them also evoke narrative locations that cover the entire world. Asian shows programmed in the OFF tend to evoke more diverse narrative locations compared to Asian productions invited in the IN. For both festivals, most African shows evoke narrative locations found within the African continent, though more outliers appear in the OFF. These findings are a first step to further analyse how representations of “elsewhere” vary within the context of European-centred performing art festivals.

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